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ABSTRACT

In free India, provincial upliftment programs were begun in 1952 under network improvement programs. These were gotten ready for changing the substance of the open nation, and building one more stance among the town individuals. Under these Five Year Plans, a serious requirement for improvement is being given to these activities. The objectives of the study are To analyse the causes of poverty in Tamil Nadu and analyse the steps to reduce poverty and people opinion about poverty alleviation in society. This study used primary data which has been collected from the 200 respondents with convenient sampling from different parts of Tamil Nadu. Information such as age, gender and the opinion on causes, effect and removal of poverty was collected. The statistical methods used by the researcher are simple percentage analysis and graphical representation.

KEYWORDS: Poverty, Economy, Schemes, Strategy, Child Labour.

INTRODUCTION

In free India, provincial upliftment programs were begun in 1952 under network improvement programs. These were gotten ready for changing the substance of the open nation, and building one more stance among the town individuals. Under these Five Year Plans, a serious requirement for improvement is being given to these activities. A lot is yet left to be done as a huge piece of people live in towns. In any case, another charge is created among the people living in villages. The destinations of the organization improvement program are extremely forceful. With the methodology of intelligent strategies for cultivating, extended making of projects and various techniques have been refined and tries go unrelenting toward this Creating neediness. Proficiency is a significant variable of neediness. Billions of individuals all over the planet live in outrageous neediness. Almost 1 out of each 10 individuals on the planet lives beneath the global destitution line. That is 689 million individuals attempting to get by on under \$1.90 per day and almost 2 billion individuals, or 26.2% of the total populace, live on under \$3.20 per day .Every year 26 million individuals fall into neediness because of catastrophic

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events. Tremors, alongside the waves they generated, killed a bigger number of individuals than any remaining sorts of calamities joined, asserting almost 750,000 lives somewhere in the range of 1994 and 2013. Although the world has gained gigantic headway on outrageous neediness decrease, progress hasn't been even. Most of the 689 million individuals actually living on under \$1.90 a day are in sub-Saharan Africa. Indeed, even among sub-Saharan superior workers like Tanzania, paces of outrageous destitution stay above 40%.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are

- To analyse the causes of poverty in Tamil Nadu,
- To analyse the steps to reduce poverty and people opinion about poverty alleviation in society

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fan and Peter (2000) have analysed the Rural India with particular reference to less favoured areas. They concluded that the poverty, food security and environmental problems of many low potential areas are likely to remain serious in the decades ahead as population continues to grow.

Mehta & Shah (2001) have discussed the present state of knowledge about chronic poverty in India. An overview of the trends in incidence of income poverty in India was provided so as to place chronic poverty in context. They try to identify the states and regions that have a high incidence of people with incomes severely below the poverty line so as to focus attention on areas that are spatial poverty traps. Attention was also drawn to the significance of identifying those who are vulnerable to risky poverty due to lack of ability to absorb the impact of shocks.

Suryanarayana (2002) have discussed such an issue in the context of strategies for and estimates of poverty reduction in the developing countries. The results were general and illustrated with reference to India. He concluded that the estimates of poverty with reference to a time-invariant calorie-intake-based norm do not show a real reduction in poverty but only a decrease in overestimation of poverty for the early years followed by its underestimation for the later years

Panagariya and Mukim (2014) have analysed poverty in India. It shows that regardless of which of the two official poverty lines there was steady decline in poverty in all states and for all social and religious groups. Accelerated growth between fiscal years 2004–2005 and 2009–2010 also led to an accelerated decline in poverty rates. Moreover, the decline in poverty rates during these years has been sharper for the socially disadvantaged groups relative to upper caste groups so that we now observe a narrowing of the gap in the poverty rates between the two sets

of social groups.

Satpathy(2019), has analysed the Poverty and Economic Growth. This study found that “urban poverty in India is over 25 percent, some 81 million people live in urban areas on incomes that are below the poverty line. At the national level, rural poverty remains higher than urban poverty, but the gap is closing.

METHODOLOGY

This study used primary data which has been collected from the 200 respondents with convenient sampling. The samples collected from the respondents are from different parts of Tamil Nadu. Information such as age, gender and the opinion on poverty was collected. The statistical methods used by the researcher are simple percentage analysis and graphical representation.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Figure 1 shows that distribution of age and their opinion about the reason for poverty. Age group of below 20 about 53.85 percent of the respondents agreed that social injustice is the reason for the poverty. In the age group of 21 to 35 majority of respondents says that less education would be the reason for the poverty, The majority of the respondents from the age group of 50 and above said that unemployment would be the reason for the poverty.

The above graph shows the age distribution and the opinion about Public Distribution System(PDS) in reducing poverty. About 47.98 respondents agreed that PDS is helpful in removing poverty from the society. In the age group of 21 to 35, almost 41.35 percent says that PDS is not helpful in removing poverty. In the age group of 36 to 50 about 21.91 gave positive result that PDS is helpful in removing poverty from the society.

The above graph shows the age distribution and their opinion about the best way to reduce poverty. About 54.08 percent of the respondents says that increasing the employment would reduce the poverty. 40 percent of the respondents says that eliminating the inequality also would be the solution to reduce poverty. Education also tool to reduce poverty.

CONCLUSION:

Around 70% of the Indian populace is living in provincial regions. Individuals in provincial regions ought to have been as old as delighted in by individuals living in rural and metropolitan regions. Besides, the falling impacts of neediness, joblessness, poor and insufficient foundation in provincial regions on metropolitan communities is prompting financial pressures showing in monetary hardship and metropolitan poverty. The articulation "provincial turn of events" is the overall advancement of rustic domains to work on the individual fulfilment of country people. The rustic formative ventures intend to decrease poverty and joblessness, to work on the prosperity and enlightening status and to fulfil the basic necessities, for instance, food, safe house and attire of the provincial people. Suggestions for the removal of poverty and its impact in India are population control, increase in employment, equal distribution of income, regional poverty, problem of distribution, fulfilment of minimum needs of the poor, increase in productivity of the poor. This study also reveals that unemployment, social injustice and lack

of education are reason for poverty. If government address the problem with proper implementation of effective schemes can reduce poverty in Tamil Nadu.

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